

Alkali Metal Complexes. Adducts of 1, 10-Phenanthroline with Alkali Metal Salts of 8-Hydroxyquinoline and *o*-Nitrobenzoic Acid

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Alkali metal salts of 8-hydroxyquinoline and *o*-nitrobenzoic acid form solid adducts with 1,10-phenanthroline in organic solvents, which are thermally very stable. Thermal, i.r., and solution studies suggest that these adducts are genuine complexes.

Hydrogen bonding is not an essential feature in forming solid alkali metal complexes.

WITH the assumption that a knowledge of the co-ordination chemistry of alkali metals would be of use in understanding more fully the absorption and transport mechanism of these metals by plants, we have synthesised and described adducts of the formula $ML_nHL^{1,2}$ and $ML.HL'^3$, where HL and HL' are oxygen and nitrogen containing ligands. Hydrogen bonding was an important feature in the solid, as judged by the i.r. spectra.

We are now extending⁴ our studies with chelating ligands devoid of acidic hydrogens, so that there be no possibility of hydrogen bonding in the complexes. The ligands we have chosen are 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline, and describe below the synthesis of adducts with alkali metal salts of 8-hydroxyquinoline and *o*-nitrobenzoic acid.

The adducts were made by adding minimum of alcohol or acetone to give a suspension of the alkali metal salt ML; solid, 1,10-phenanthroline (*phen*), or 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline was then added in the mole ratio 4:1 of the salt. All the solids went into solution. Frequently some crystals were deposited after a few minutes but these were redissolved on heating. The mixture was warmed for 5 min, on a steam bath, then allowed to cool, and the resulting crystals filtered, washed with cold alcohol or acetone and dried in an oven. The compounds and their analyses are given in Table as are the colours of the adducts. Colour changes were shown by the metal-8-hydroxyquinolinates, the salts of which are off-white. The solids on heating transformed at temperatures greatly in excess of the melting point of 1,10-phenanthroline (116°) as shown in the Table. The transformation gave another solid which melted at the same temperature as ML.

Organic solvents decompose the adduct, depositing ML, while water deposits *phen*. However, the adducts do dissolve in *N*-methylpyrrolidone in which solvent their conductivities were measured, the values are given in the Table, with those of ML, for comparison. For the anhydrous *phen*. adducts the conductivities do not differ significantly from

those of ML, indicating that the adduct is probably completely dissociated in *N*-methylpyrrolidone which is a solvent for both compounds.

It appears that the adduct formation is essentially a solid state phenomenon. It is possible that the adducts are molecular complexes formed between planar chelated anions and planar phenanthroline molecule, but two pieces of evidence suggest that the phenanthroline is probably chelated to the cation. Firstly, attempts to prepare the 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline analogue of the Rb-oxinate, having more than one *phen*. per cation, gave only the 1:1 compound; this suggests that the steric hindrance by the methyl groups prevents coordination by more than one of these ligands. This steric hindrance would apply even if the alkali metal is not coplanar with the *phen*. molecule. The second piece of evidence is that the i.r. spectra resemble that of transition metal *phen*. chelates⁵, in showing shifts and splittings of the ligand bands at 738, 854 and 1505 cm^{-1} ; observed values in these regions are given in the Table. The i.r. spectra of the adducts are diagnostically different from those of mixtures of ML and *phen*.

It is difficult to remove the water (or ethanol) from the solvated compounds, heating to 100° proving ineffective, probably those molecules are also coordinated to the metal. No hydrogen bonded OH stretching frequencies were found in the 1700-2900 cm^{-1} region.

The adducts are characterised as true compounds by (a) the stoichiometric mixtures had a lower melting point, and (b) mixtures had different molecular vibrations (i.r.). The existence of an interaction was demonstrated by the solubilisation of the suspended alkali metal salt on addition of *phen*. or 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline during the preparation of the adduct. As in the ML_nHL and $ML.HL'$ series when ML was the *m*-nitrobenzoate of the metal, no adduct was formed. We cannot yet be certain whether preliminary chelation by the metal is essential to adduct formation.

TABLE—SOME PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA

Compound	Colour	Transition temperature (°C)	c	Found %				Calculated %				Selected i.r. absorption band (cm ⁻¹)		
				Adduct	M L	C	H	N	Metal	C	H		H	Metal
HL = 8-Hydroxy-quinoline														
LiL(phen) ₂ H ₂ O ^a	Pale yellow	205-08	21	6	73.7	4.4	10.8	74.1	4.4	12.3	840, 822	740, 730	1510, 1495	
NaL(phen) ^a	Deep yellow	170-72	8	6	74.1	4.3	12.4	72.6	4.0	12.1	844	738, 733	1505, 1490	
KL(phen) ₂ H ₂ O ^a	Dirty yellow	195-98	16	15	68.4	4.0	10.9	69.8	4.0	11.3	847, 837	728	1500, 1490	
RbL(phen) ₂	Dirty yellow	160-62	18	18	66.9	3.9	11.7	67.1	3.7	11.8	854, 846	736, 733	1510, 1500	
sL(phen)	Dirty yellow	148-50	17	18	55.4	3.2	8.8	55.1	3.0	9.1	840	742, 732	1505, 1495	
HL = <i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid														
LiL(phen) ^a	White	235			66.1	3.5	11.6	64.6	3.4	11.9	858, 848, 834	722	1506, 1500	
NaL(phen) ^a	Dirty white	135-40			61.6	3.9	10.8	61.8	3.3	11.4	856, 845	729	1515	
KL(phen) ^a	Dirty white	120-22			60.1	3.3	10.5	59.2	3.1	10.9	858	742		
RbL(phen) ^b	White	175			56.1	3.2	9.7	52.9	2.8	9.7	851, 838	726	1506	
CsL(phen) ^b	White	135			47.6	3.1	8.7	47.7	2.5	8.8	845		1505	
1,10-Phenanthroline		115-17									854	738	1505	

^a—Preparation of the complex in acetone^b—Preparation of the complex in ethanol.

Our present work shows that hydrogen bonding is not necessary for formation of adducts between a chelating ligand and the alkali metal salt of a chelate anion. It may be that hydrogen bonding is one of the structure forming features of the ML.HL' and ML.*n*HL adducts. In general, the difference between the melting point of *phen.* and the transition temperature of its adducts is greater than between the melting points of HL or HL' and the transition temperatures of the corresponding adducts, perhaps an indication of greater strength in the weakest adduct-forming bond in the *phen.* system.

Experimental

The synthetic method was the same for all the systems, apart from the reaction medium which was alcohol or acetone, as indicated in the Table. Acetone was used when no adduct could be isolated from alcohol; in these cases suspensions of ML in alcohol were solubilised by addition of *phen.*, but no subsequent crystallisation took place. Successful syntheses were carried out by making a very concentrated solution of ML in the medium, usually with additional solid in suspension, then adding *phen.* or 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-*phen.* in a molar excess of 4 : 1. Greater excess was avoided to prevent crystallisation of the base in preference to the adduct. The mixture was warmed for 5 min on a steam bath and all the solids dissolved. On cooling crystals separated,

these were filtered off, washed with cold alcohol and dried in an oven at 80°. Analytical figures are given in the Table.

In a typical preparation 150 mg. of pale yellow sodium oxinate were suspended in 5 ml. of absolute alcohol and 500 mg. of solid *phen.* was added. When the mixture was stirred slowly, all the solid dissolved giving a pale yellow solution which on standing deposited a deep yellow solid. This solid was redissolved by warming the mixture on a steam-bath for 5 min. On cooling, deep yellow crystals were obtained. These were washed with cold alcohol, and dried in an oven at 80°.

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